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Analyzing the Role of Digital India in the Manufacturing Sector and its Impact on India's Sustainable Development: A Perspective on Green Logistics

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ABSTRACT

Digital India is a government initiative aimed at creating a more digitally connected, inclusive, and sustainable economy. This study analyses the impact of the manufacturing sector on India's Sustainable Development and the role of green logistics after Digital India. The study utilizes secondary data from various sources. In this study, SPSS was used to perform tests for correlation, regression, ANOVA and Durbin Watson Test. The correlation analysis reveals a strong positive relationship between MVA and GVA at basic prices, which is highly significant. This suggests that changes in MVA are closely linked to fluctuations in GVA at basic prices. The R-square value indicates that 86.7% of the variation in GVA at basic prices can be explained by the variation in MVA. The results indicate that the regression model is statistically significant, confirming that the model fits the data well. The regression coefficients suggest that an increase in MVA positively impacts India's GVA at basic prices. The analysis also suggests no significant autocorrelation in the residuals, ensuring the reliability of the model. The residual statistics also confirm that the model fits well, showing that the predictions made by the model are closely aligned with the actual data. The results confirm the alternative hypothesis suggesting that MVA has a significant impact on India's GVA at basic prices after Digital India.

In conclusion, the integration of digital technologies and green logistics enhances operational efficiency, reduces environmental impact and optimises resource utilisation in India's manufacturing sector. This combination not only accelerates economic growth by boosting productivity but also aligns with sustainability goals, fostering long-term development and supporting India's vision for a green economy.

Keywords: Manufacturing Value Added, Green Logistics, India, Sustainable Development, Digital India

INTRODUCTION

Digital India has transformed the economic framework of the nation by driving innovation, enhancing connectivity, and increasing efficiency across various sectors. This flagship initiative by the Government of India focuses on building a society that is digitally empowered and driven by knowledge. By integrating advanced technologies, Digital India bridges the digital divide, strengthens governance, and promotes inclusive growth. The manufacturing sector is one of the key beneficiaries of these advancements, playing a crucial role in India's economy and serving as a major driver of sustainable development. The manufacturing sector plays a significant role in contributing to India's GVA, employment creation and export earnings. However, this sector faces persistent challenges, including inefficiencies in resource utilisation, high production costs, and environmental concerns. The integration of digital technologies has revolutionised the sector. These technologies enable smart manufacturing processes that enhance productivity, optimise resource use, and minimise waste. The robust digital infrastructure developed under the Digital India initiative, including high-speed internet and advanced digital platforms, supports this transformation by enabling industries to implement sustainable practices on a wider scale.

Green logistics has emerged as a vital component of sustainable manufacturing. Green logistics focuses on minimizing the environmental footprint of manufacturing by improving supply chain efficiency, reducing carbon emissions, and promoting eco-friendly practices. Technologies such as blockchain for transparent tracking and predictive analytics for proactive planning empower businesses to adopt green logistics effectively and achieve their sustainability goals.

The integration of digital manufacturing and green logistics not only addresses environmental challenges but also fosters economic growth. Efficient logistics systems reduce operational costs, enhance delivery processes, and improve the global competitiveness of Indian manufacturers. Complementary initiatives under Digital India, such as Smart Cities and e-governance, create a supportive ecosystem for sustainable industrial activities, fostering innovation and investment.

In conclusion, Digital India is redefining the manufacturing sector by combining technological advancements with sustainability. By leveraging digital technologies and adopting green logistics, India is striving to balance economic growth with environmental conservation, laying the foundation for a sustainable and inclusive future.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

R. Abdullah, M.S. Mat Daud, F. Ahmad, and A.A. Shukti (2016) focused on green practices in relation to customer satisfaction, logistics operations, and amenities, highlighting their environmental and operational benefits. The study identified EMS and GSCM as key factors driving sustainable practices. It emphasized both the benefits and challenges of green logistics in meeting customer needs while reducing environmental impact. ¹

John C. Anyanwu (2017) analysed the factors influencing manufacturing value added (MVA). The study identified secondary education, trade openness, FDI, ICT infrastructure, and population size as positive contributors to MVA, while reliance on oil and gas rents, civil violence, and weak democracy were found to hinder it. A cubic relationship between MVA and economic development was established, emphasizing the need for structural transformation and strategic policies to boost manufacturing growth and create quality jobs for the region's youth. ²

Muhammad Ashfaq, Imran Qureshi, Sobia Irum, Nasir Mehmood, Nohman Khan and Humara Ahmad (2020) examine that green logistics practices, when integrated with environmental collaboration, significantly enhance sustainability performance in Malaysian manufacturing companies. Their research indicates that effective environmental collaboration with suppliers leads to improved sustainability outcomes. The study also demonstrates that green logistics methods have a beneficial influence on company environmental performance, emphasising the need of implementing sustainable practices in the industrial sector to obtain long-term environmental and financial advantages. ³

Keerthana P. Girijan (2024) examines the Digital India initiative's role in promoting sustainable, affordable, and citizen-centric technologies. It has transformed lives at the grassroots, responding to crises, and contributing to citizens' well-being. The study highlights the alignment of the Digital India initiative with the UN SDGs, advancing India's progress towards Agenda 2030. ⁴

Himakshi Goswami (2016) explores the Digital India Programme, emphasising its potential to promote digital inclusion and boost economic growth. While it aims to integrate government services and reduce paperwork, challenges like infrastructure gaps and digital literacy must be addressed. Despite these, the programme offers significant opportunities for citizens' socio-economic development.

Mohammad Karami, Naser Elahinia, and Shekoufeh Karami (2019) revealed a significantly positive relationship between economic growth, manufacturing, labour force, and

technology, while investment demonstrated a negative association with growth. They concluded that policymakers should prioritize policies that enhance manufacturing productivity and employment to achieve sustainable and competitive economic development. The study utilized a model combining Kaldor's growth law and the neoclassical growth model for econometric analysis. 6

Yash Mehta and John Rajan A (2017) examine the growth strategies of India's manufacturing sector, emphasising the role of infrastructure, tax and labour law compliance, and environmental standards in state-level performance. They highlight Gujarat and Andhra Pradesh as strong performers. The study also discusses the impact of reforms like the GST bill in streamlining logistics and fostering sectoral growth. Improved infrastructure, industrial corridors, and transport networks are identified as critical enablers for India to emerge as a manufacturing hub. 7

Salimatu Rufai Mohammed and Ummi Ibrahim (2022) analysed the factors influencing sector performance using Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) modelling. According to their findings, debt, imports, FDI, and GFCF have a negative long-run influence on sector performance but exports and external reserves have a favourable impact. They recommend directing external funds from debt and FDI towards sector development, minimising imports of manufactured goods, and promoting exports to enhance sector performance. 8

Meraa Divi Pannirselvan, Syed Radzi Bin Rahamaddulla, Puteri Fadzline Muuhamad, Mohd Ghazali Maarof, and Shahryar Sorooshian (2016) examine the growing importance of logistics in the technology-driven economy, particularly in addressing environmental issues in industries. It also highlights that limiting distribution trips to reduce carbon footprints is the most effective strategy for implementing green logistics in the sector. 9

Sneha Sharad Pawar (2018) examines the factors influencing growth in India's manufacturing sector post-1991 reforms, highlighting that output growth is predominantly input-driven rather than efficiency-driven. The study emphasizes the role of structural reforms, investment climate, and production efficiency in fostering competitiveness. It underscores the importance of developing, importing, and adapting new technologies to enhance efficiency. The study thoroughly examines various theories specific to India and provides suggestions to enhance productivity and ensure sustained growth in the manufacturing sector over time. 10

Jyoti Sharma (2016) examines the Digital India Programme as a transformative initiative aimed at creating a digitally empowered society. The program enhances governance through technology, promoting transparency, accountability, and streamlined services. It strives to improve citizens' quality of life and ensure equal access, contributing to societal empowerment and development. 11

Veera Pandiyan Kaliani Sundram, Atikah Shamsul Bahrin, Akmal Aini Othman, and Zarina Abdul Munir (2017) emphasise that practices like green purchasing, eco-design, reverse logistics, and customer cooperation significantly enhance environmental and operational outcomes, underlining the importance of sustainable practices in improving manufacturing performance. 12

RESEARCH GAP

After reviewing the existing literature, it is evident that while extensive research has focused on the Digital India Programme and its effects on technology and economic growth, there is a lack of studies examining its specific role in promoting sustainable development. Although green logistics has been researched in the manufacturing sectors of other countries such as Malaysia and Europe, its integration within India's manufacturing sector, particularly in the context of Digital India, remains underexplored. Additionally, while the association between MVA and economic growth has been analyzed, there is limited research on how MVA affects India's Gross Value Added at basic prices after Digital India. This research seeks to fill these

gaps by examining how Digital India has influenced the economic performance of India’s manufacturing sector and contributed to sustainable development through the use of green logistics practices.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study is valuable as it examines how digital transformation can promote sustainable growth in India’s manufacturing sector. The manufacturing sector is integral to India’s overall economic performance, with its growth directly influencing GVA, employment, and industrial output. This study looks at how digital technologies are being integrated into manufacturing and logistics, showing how green logistics can reduce environmental harm, optimize resource utilization and contribute to India’s sustainable development. The research offers valuable insights for policymakers, industry leaders, and environmental stakeholders, demonstrating how digital tools can enhance manufacturing efficiency while ensuring sustainability. The findings will help shape strategies that balance economic growth with ecological responsibility, fostering a competitive, resource- efficient, and environmentally-conscious manufacturing ecosystem.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To provide an overview of India's manufacturing value added from 2015-2016 to 2022-2023.
2. To examine the impact of the MVA on India's GVA at basic prices after Digital India.
3. To evaluate the role of green logistics in India’s manufacturing sector and its contribution to India's sustainable development.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of the MVA on India's GVA at basic prices after Digital India.

H₁₁: There is a significant impact of the MVA on India's GVA at basic prices after Digital India.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

This study aims to analyse the impact of MVA on India’s GVA at Basic Prices after Digital India with a focus on the role of green logistics in the manufacturing sector and its contribution to India's sustainable development. The research primarily relies on secondary data sources from reputable organizations such as the World Bank, which provides data from 2015 to 2023. In this research, SPSS software is used to calculate correlation, regression analysis, ANOVA and the Durbin-Watson test to examine the impact of the MVA on India's GVA at basic prices after Digital India.

OVERVIEW OF INDIA'S MANUFACTURING VALUE ADDED FROM 2015-2016 TO 2022-2023

Table 1: India's Manufacturing Value Added From 2015-2016 to 2022-2023

YEAR	MVA (CURRENT US \$ BILLION)	MVA GROWTH (%)
2015-16	347.94	6.14%
2016-17	398.20	14.45%
2017-18	402.24	1.01%
2018-19	381.55	-5.14%
2019-20	377.70	-1.01%
2020-21	455.36	20.56%
2021-22	440.06	-3.36%
2022-23	461.38	4.84%

Source: World Bank Data

Figure 1: India's Manufacturing Value Added From 2015-2016 to 2022-2023

Source: World Bank Data

According to Figure 1, the trends in Manufacturing Value Added show notable fluctuations over the years. In 2015-16, the value stood at US \$ 347.94 billion, reflecting a growth rate of 6.14%. The growth continued in 2016-17, where the value increased significantly to US \$ 398.20 billion, marking a growth of 14.45%. However, in 2017-18, the growth slowed down, with the value rising to US \$ 402.24 billion, reflecting a modest growth rate of 1.01%. The following year, 2018-19, saw a decline, with the value dropping to US \$ 381.55 billion, showing a negative growth rate of -5.14%. In 2019-20, the trend continued with a slight decrease to US \$ 377.70 billion, reflecting a -1.01% decline. A strong recovery occurred in 2020-21, with the value rising to US \$ 455.36 billion, showing a significant growth rate of 20.56%. However, in 2021-22, the value fell slightly to US \$ 440.06 billion, reflecting a decline of -3.36%. Finally, in 2022-23, the value rebounded to US \$ 461.38 billion, showing a growth of 4.84%. These fluctuations suggest varying trends in the manufacturing sector, influenced by economic factors, global conditions, and policy changes.

Table 2: Variables Used In the Study (Amount In Current Us \$ Billion)

YEAR	MANUFACTURING, VALUE ADDED	INDIA'S GVA AT BASIC PRICES
2015-16	347.94	2080
2016-17	398.2	2410
2017-18	402.24	2460
2018-19	381.55	2590
2019-20	377.7	2450
2020-21	455.36	2900
2021-22	440.06	3070
2022-23	461.38	3230

Source: World Bank Data

Table 3: Correlation Results Between MVA And India's GVA At Basic Prices

		MVA (CURRENT US \$ BILLION)	INDIA'S GVA AT BASIC PRICES (CURRENT US \$ BILLION)
MVA (CURRENT US \$ BILLION)	Pearson Correlation	1	.931**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	8	8
INDIA'S GVA AT BASIC PRICES (CURRENT US \$ BILLION)	Pearson Correlation	.931**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	8	8

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), Source: SPSS output

Table 4: Regression Model Summary for MVA and India’s GVA at Basic Prices

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.931 ^a	.867	.845	151.644	1.981

- a. Predictors: (Constant), MVA (Current US \$ Billion)
- b. Dependent Variable: India's GVA at Basic Prices (Current US \$ Billion) Source: SPSS output

Table 5: Analysis Of Variance for MVA and India’s GVA at Basic Prices

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	899511.268	1	899511.268	39.116	.001 ^b
	Residual	137976.232	6	22996.039		
	Total	1037487.500	7			

- a. Dependent Variable: India's GVA at Basic Prices (Current US \$ Billion)
- b. Predictors: (Constant), MVA (Current US \$ Billion) Source: SPSS output

Table 6: Coefficients

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-964.159	580.153		-1.662	.148
	MVA (CURRENT US \$ BILLION)	8.854	1.416	.931	6.254	.001

Dependent Variable: India's GVA at Basic Prices (Current US \$ Billion) Source: SPSS output

Table 7: Residual Statistics

Residuals Statistics ^a					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	2116.50	3120.90	2648.75	358.471	8
Residual	-167.600	175.914	.000	140.395	8
Std. Predicted Value	-1.485	1.317	.000	1.000	8
Std. Residual	-1.105	1.160	.000	.926	8

- a. Dependent Variable: India's GVA at Basic Prices (Current US \$ Billion) Source: SPSS output

INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF THE MANUFACTURING VALUE ADDED ON INDIA'S GROSS VALUE ADDED AT BASIC PRICES AFTER DIGITAL INDIA

According to Table 3, the correlation analysis between India's manufacturing value added and its Gross Value Added (GVA) at basic prices reveals a strong positive relationship. The correlation coefficient of 0.931 is highly significant, with a p-value of 0.001 indicating that changes in manufacturing value added are closely associated with fluctuations in GVA at basic prices. According to Table 4, the regression model summary shows an R-value of 0.931, emphasising a strong relationship between manufacturing value added and GVA at basic prices. The R-squared value of 0.867 suggests that 86.7% of the variation in GVA at basic prices can be explained by changes in manufacturing value added. The Adjusted R-squared value of 0.845 accounts for the number of predictors, further supporting the model’s goodness of fit. The Standard Error of the Estimate is 151.644, and the Durbin-Watson statistic is 1.981, indicating no significant autocorrelation in the residuals which supports the reliability of the model's predictions. According to Table 5, the ANOVA results demonstrate that the regression model is statistically significant, with an F-statistic of 39.116 and a p-value of 0.001, confirming that the model provides a good fit to the data. According to Table 6, the coefficients show that the

unstandardized coefficient for manufacturing value added is 8.854, meaning that for every US \$ 1 billion increase in manufacturing value added, GVA at basic prices is expected to rise by US \$ 8.854 billion. The standardized coefficient (Beta) is 0.931 and the t-statistic is 6.254, significant at the 0.001 level, confirming the strength of the relationship. According to Table 7, the residual statistics show that the predicted values of GVA at basic prices range from US \$ 2116.50 billion to US \$ 3120.90 billion, with a mean of US \$ 2648.70 billion. The residuals have a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of US \$ 140.395 billion, indicating that the model fits the data well. The standardized residuals range from -1.485 to 1.317, with a mean of 0, suggesting that the residuals are well-distributed and within an acceptable range. The results confirm the alternative hypothesis suggesting that MVA has a significant impact on India's GVA at basic prices after Digital India.

ROLE OF GREEN LOGISTICS IN INDIA'S MANUFACTURING SECTOR AND ITS CONTRIBUTION TO INDIA'S SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Green logistics is key to transforming India's manufacturing industry and helping the country achieve its sustainability goals. By focusing on reducing the environmental impact of supply chain activities, it incorporates practices like energy-efficient transportation, sustainable packaging, and better waste management. These strategies are essential for reducing carbon emissions, conserving resources, and promoting a circular economy, all of which are critical to India's long-term sustainability goals.

In India's manufacturing sector, green logistics addresses key environmental challenges such as high fuel consumption, waste generation, and inefficient resource use. The use of fuel-efficient vehicles, optimized transportation routes, and renewable energy sources significantly reduces the carbon footprint of logistics operations. The adoption of sustainable packaging, including biodegradable and recyclable materials, along with recycling initiatives to minimize waste, further helps in mitigating environmental harm. These practices align with global environmental standards and enhance the global competitiveness of India's manufacturing sector. From an economic perspective, green logistics offers substantial benefits. Streamlined operations and energy-efficient practices lead to cost savings for manufacturers, making the sector more competitive. Businesses that implement green logistics practices are better positioned to meet international environmental regulations, which makes them more attractive to global markets that prioritise sustainability. This strengthens India's manufacturing sector, positioning it as a global leader in sustainable industrial practices. The Digital India initiative highlights the crucial role of technology in driving green logistics. The integration of the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence and blockchain is increasingly improving the efficiency and environmental sustainability of logistics operations. IoT allows for real-time tracking of goods and routes, while AI helps streamline delivery schedules and predict when vehicles need maintenance. Blockchain increases visibility and accountability, helping to ensure sustainable practices are upheld across the entire supply chain. Additionally, smart warehousing, powered by automation and renewable energy, helps further reduce energy consumption and minimize waste.

CONCLUSION

This paper analyses the relationship between India's manufacturing value added and its Gross Value Added at Basic Prices after Digital India with a focus on the role of green logistics in the manufacturing sector and its contribution to India's sustainable development. The analysis shows a strong and positive correlation between MVA and India's GVA at basic prices. The results of the regression analysis support the alternative hypothesis that manufacturing value

added has a significant impact on India's GVA at basic prices. The model's statistical significance, along with its high explanatory power, confirms that changes in manufacturing value added to account for a large portion of the variation in India's GVA at basic prices. The robustness of the model is further validated by the absence of significant autocorrelation in the residuals, confirming the accuracy of the predictions. The results confirm the alternative hypothesis suggesting that MVA has a significant impact on India's GVA at basic prices after Digital India. This reinforces the importance of the manufacturing sector, especially when enhanced by green logistics and the Digital India initiative, in driving economic growth and contributing to sustainable development.

Green logistics plays a crucial role in transforming India's manufacturing sector and contributing to its sustainable development. By adopting eco-friendly practices like energy-efficient transportation, sustainable packaging, and waste management, logistics operations can greatly reduce their environmental impact. These strategies help cut down carbon emissions, conserve resources, and support a circular economy, all of which are crucial for achieving India's long-term sustainability goals. In the manufacturing sector, green logistics addresses critical challenges like high fuel consumption, waste generation, and resource inefficiency. The integration of renewable energy, fuel-efficient vehicles, and optimized transportation routes helps reduce the carbon footprint of logistics activities. Moreover, the adoption of sustainable packaging materials and waste reduction initiatives, such as recycling, further minimises environmental harm and aligns with global standards. Economically, green logistics provides cost savings through streamlined operations and energy-efficient practices, improving the sector's competitiveness. The integration of advanced technologies like IoT, AI, and blockchain, particularly under the Digital India initiative, enhances operational efficiency and sustainability. These technologies enable real-time tracking, optimized delivery schedules, and improved transparency in the supply chain.

In conclusion, green logistics is vital for India's sustainable development. By integrating eco-friendly practices and leveraging digital technologies, it reduces environmental impact while fostering economic growth, positioning India as a leader in sustainable industrial practices.

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India's Gross Value Added at Basic Prices (Current US \$ Billion)

<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.FCST.CD?end=2023&locations=IN>

<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.FCST.CD?end=2023&locations=IN>

Manufacturing, Value Added (Current US \$ Billion)

<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NV.IND.MANF.CD?end=2023&locations=IN>

<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NV.IND.MANF.CD?end=2023&locations=IN>